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Socio-demographic Determinants of Utilization of Maternal Healthcare Services in Sub-saharan Africa: A Brief Review

Emaediong I. Akpanekpo¹, Ekaette Umoessien²

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Utilisation of maternal healthcare services is important for optimization of maternal health during and beyond pregnancy.

Methodology: Review on the available literature on the subject was done through Medline, Google Search using the following keywords: utilisation, socio-demographic, maternal healthcare, Africa

Results: Utilisation of maternal healthcare services is influenced by socio-demographic determinants.

Conclusion: The distribution of maternal healthcare services utilization varies with age, place of residence, socio-economic strata and level of education.

Keyword: maternal health, utilisation, Socio-demographic determinants

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INTRODUCTION

Maternal mortality is a significant public health concern and has been a priority for global bodies and many governments¹. The World Health Organization estimates that women die each year from pregnancy related causes and almost all of these deaths occur in developing countries². Nigeria is a developing country and has quite a significant amount of deaths from maternal mortality³. The causes of maternal mortality are directly from obstetric complications or factors related to pregnancy or health seeking behavior.

The benefits of utilizing maternal healthcare services are enormous. There is evidence to prove that most

obstetric complications are preventable and treatable through the utilization of maternal healthcare services. Furthermore, it gives the opportunity to be informed about the danger signs and symptoms of pregnancy and the risks of labour and delivery. It helps women attain the delivery of the baby with the assistance of skilled healthcare providers. Healthcare facilities offer the opportunity for passing on health information to enhance well-being and prevention of malaria, tuberculosis, tetanus and HIV infections - especially through ante-natal care services⁴.

II. Socio-demographic Determinants of Maternal Healthcare Services Utilization

Age

Younger and middle aged mothers are more likely to seek pregnancy related care services from skilled attendants compared to women aged 34 years and above⁵. Health seeking behavior has been found to increase with younger age and decrease with older age⁶. Older women have been found to be reluctant in seeking healthcare but preferred to deliver at home with the assistance of a traditional birth attendant⁷. Other studies also reported that women in

extremes of their reproductive age utilized MH care services more than those in the middle of their reproductive age.^{5,8}

There have however been opposing reports with studies that put confounding factors into consideration. It was reported that young mothers' maternal healthcare utilization is a function of affordability rather than age⁹. Other studies have found no significant differences between young and old mothers with respect to seeking antenatal services¹⁰.

Education

Women education has been shown to increase the use of maternal care services¹¹. Educated women are more likely than uneducated women to use antenatal care; to use it early and frequently; and to use trained providers and institutions¹².

Few studies were able to delineate the level of education to positive associations with maternal health services utilization. In Nepal, it was reported that women with more than primary level of education are more likely to use antenatal care services than those with no education¹³. In Turkey, it was reported that women with more than six years of schooling were more likely to use antenatal care than those without¹¹.

In studies where other variables were controlled, statistically significant difference was still found between level of education and maternal healthcare services utilization¹⁴. Studies have also found an association between use of skilled birth attendants and use of health facility for delivery and level of education of the head of households¹⁵.

Education is believed to improve MH care service utilization by the increased level of health awareness and greater knowledge of available health services among educated women, increased knowledge of benefits of maternal care services, improved ability of educated women to afford the cost of medical health-care and their enhanced level of autonomy¹⁶.

Place of Residence

Place of residence has been found to influence the utilization of maternal healthcare services. Women who live in rural areas have been found to less likely give birth in a health facility compared to their urban counterparts^{17, 16}. Studies have also reported that women who live in rural areas have less odds of delivery by assistance with health professionals compared to urban women¹⁴. Women living in urban areas have been associated with higher odds of delivery in a healthcare facility¹⁸.

Some explanations have been postulated as to why rural women utilize maternal services less. Women in rural areas rate the services of traditional birth attendants as being of higher quality than that of medical health-care providers, particularly with regards to interpersonal communication and relationship^{16, 8, 19}. Other studies attribute low maternal care utilization in most rural communities to the belief that pregnancy is a natural process requiring no medical intervention and low awareness of benefits of antenatal care¹⁶.

Socio-economic Status

Economic stability has been identified as an important factor that influences maternal healthcare utilization behavior of women. Studies have shown that a higher percentage of people with more income had access to healthcare professionals during delivery^{20, 14}. Women with lower

standards of living had significantly lesser odds of delivery in a health facility¹⁰.

Explanations for the positive association between financial strength and maternal healthcare services utilization have been postulated. Besides paying for direct services

offered by clinics, women have to also pay for indirect and related costs such as transportation and food. Also, anticipation of high cost will affect whether a decision to go

Marital status

Marital status influences the choice of delivery either through influence on female autonomy or through financial resources. Single and divorced women have more autonomy than

to a health facility should be made or not. Women with more financial power are better equipped to overcome potential cost barriers⁶.

married women²¹. Young single mothers may be cared for by their family members who may encourage skilled birth delivery.

CONCLUSION

The distribution of maternal healthcare services utilization varies with age, place of residence, socio-economic strata and level of education. Education of mothers is important to achieving more utilization of maternal healthcare services and reducing maternal mortality. Women living in rural areas

and of low financial strength are at a disadvantage. Delivery assistance services should be made affordable and accessible for them.

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